

Transformational leadership and transactional leadership styles: systematic review of literature

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ABSTRACT

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The significance of some factors related to leadership styles remains a critical supportive element in an organization. The absence of these factors might negatively affect deliverables. This study aims to systematically review the literature on transformational leadership styles and transactional leadership styles in an organization. The data for the paper were from the available web of knowledge literature on transformational leadership styles and transactional leadership styles. Google Scholar discovered 19,600 results, reviewed articles 1,770 results, and only 780 results for sort by relevance. The researchers selected 50 articles from among 155 papers uncovered in the databases and somehow related to the object of study. The systematic review research appraised articles from 2019 focusing on the components of transformational leadership and transactional leadership styles. Overall systematic literature review showed that transformational leadership encourages higher levels of innovation and creativity measured by divergent thinking among group members. On the other hand, the ability of leaders to properly implement transformational and transactional leadership styles can lead to higher followers' trust in the leaders.

Introduction

The general well-being of organizations and societies is immensely contingent on a range of variables with leadership top on the list. Leadership is perhaps one of the most important aspects of management (Wehrich *et al.*, 2008). Through the effective leadership of Jack Welch and Lee Iacocca, companies like General Electric and Chrysler were brought back from the edge of bankruptcy to become two of the most lucrative companies in the world (Robbins & Coulter, 2007). Also, due to effective leadership, great nations like the United States of America, Britain, France, and India are among the most recognized in the world today (Wehrich *et al.*, 2008). This paper defines leadership as the process of influencing groups to achieve goals, while a leader is someone who can influence others (Cole, 2006; Robbin and Coulter, 2007; Wehrich *et al.*, 2008). The developing attention in literature for transformational and transactional leadership has strengthened the field of leadership and attracted several new scholars to the field (Hunt, 1999). For instance, a comprehensive 10-year review of the articles published in the Leadership Quarterly, (Lowe and Gardner, 2000) found the transformational leadership paradigm was the most researched area of leadership over the last decade.

The impact of transformational and transactional leader behaviors on salespeople's organizational attitudes and performances are covered in this study, along with the moderating effect that trust and role ambiguity play. Whereas majority of authors agree that transactional and transformational leadership differ in theoretical and practical methodologies, many remain consistent with the claim that transformational leadership significantly enhances transactional leadership, leading to higher levels of individual, group, and organizational performance (Bass & Avolio, 1994; Howell & Avolio, 1993; Lowe *et al.*, 1996). Others believe that Transactional leadership is a subset of transformational leadership (Wehrich *et al.*, 2008). The purpose of this paper is to conduct a systematic review of related literature for a comparative analysis between transactional and transformational leadership styles. This paper outlined and explained transactional and transformational leadership styles in the literature review.

Review of literature

Leadership styles

Several theories have and are being put forward to explain leadership effectiveness. Two of the most prominent leadership theories are transformational

and transactional leadership theories. The individual leadership style notably remains a combination of their beliefs, values and preferences. The systematic review focused on relevant literature using a comprehensive, preplanned approach to find existing literature, assess its contributions, analyze and synthesize findings and report on evidences to allow conclusions to be reached about what is known and what is not (Denyer & Tranfield, 2009).

Transformational leadership style

James Macgregor Burns introduced the idea of transformational leadership in 1978, in his descriptive research on political leaders, but its usage has spread into organizational psychology and management with further modifications by Bass and Avolio (1997). Since the late 1980s, theories of transformational and transactional leadership have been ascendant and “the single most studied and debated idea with the field of leadership” (Diaz-Saenz, 2011). A transformational leader is a person who stimulates and inspires (transform) followers to achieve extraordinary outcomes (Robbins and Coulter, 2007). Versions of transformational leadership have been proposed by several theorists, including Bass (1985, 1996). The four dimensions of transformational leadership are Charisma or idealized influence, Personal and Individual attention, inspirational motivation, and intellectual stimulation. For the past fifteen years plus, considerable proof has been gathered supporting Bass’ original contention with studies conducted in a very broad range of organizational settings (Avolio, 1999; Bass, 1998).

Transformational leaders serve as mentors to their followers by promoting learning, success, and personal growth. They create context, serve as role models, present obstacles, arouse feelings, and promote an environment of trust (Bass & Avolio, 1997). For example, the influence of nurse leadership style on the culture of patient safety incident reporting: systematic review reflects that despite the use of incident reporting systems, the culture of patient safety reporting is still lacking (Gong et al., 2017). Archer et al. (2017) found that around 50-96% of patient safety incidents in the United States (US) are not reported, with the main obstacles to reporting being fear of adverse consequences, overcomplicated reporting processes and systems, and the nature of the incidents themselves. Leithwood and Montgomery (1982), among others, identified a strong, directive leadership style that focused on curriculum and instruction in the

principals of elementary schools who were effective in teaching the children of poor urban communities in the U.S. This model became very popular in schools globally until the 1990s, when scholars and practitioners began to popularize terms such as shared leadership, teacher leadership, distributed leadership, and transformational leadership.

Transformational leaders impact their followers through various behaviors. In fact, (MacKenzie, Moorman & Fetter's (1990) review of the leadership literature by Podsakoff shows that transformational leaders can inspire followers to perform above and beyond expectations by articulating a vision, serving as a suitable role model, facilitating affirmation of group goals, offering individualized support and encouragement, and displaying high performance standards, As a result, the processes by which they operate are different, and the forms of transformational leadership behaviors are distinct. Group members become more responsible because they are inspired, and they engage in more constructive behavior such as organizational citizenship behavior or helping out even without the promise of a reward (Ronald and Jason 2006). Workers who report to transformational leaders are even more likely to have a positive mood throughout the workday (Joyce, Hannah, Gregory & John 2007). Four components of transformational leadership styles were identified by Warrilow (2012). The transformational leadership components are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: The transformational leadership components

This refers to the extent to which leaders behaviors cause followers to challenge their assumptions, think creatively, take risks, and participate intellectually providing a framework to see how they connect to each other and the goal. Avolio and Bass (1988) claim that intellectual stimulation results in a "cognitive evaluation of current conditions," perhaps reversing ones. It is likely that this approach is unsatisfactory and that leaders who

consistently use this leadership style are perceived as being unreliable, unpredictable, and/or hard to please. Short-term consequences could include an increase in role ambiguity, conflict, or stress as well as a decline in trust and pleasure. However, if intellectual stimulation prompts salespeople to evaluate out various strategies or methods, some of which may prove to be more successful than the ones they are currently doing, the results could be positive.

Charisma or Idealized influence

This highlights the degree to which the leader behaves in admirable ways and displays convictions and takes stands that cause followers to identify with the leader who has a clear set of values and acts as a role model for the followers. Reflecting the extent to which a leader attends to the needs and concerns of his or her followers by providing socio-emotional support. It involves mentoring followers, maintaining frequent contact, encouraging followers to self-actualize, and empowering them. The need for performing effectively may be especially acute in the context of sales because of the high emotional demands placed on salespeople by their jobs' unpredictable ups and downs as well as the inherent stress of their boundary-spanning positions. The practitioner literature (e.g., Pacetta 1994:42, 55, 58) however, without a doubt, acknowledge the need of individualized support in assisting sales managers in inspiring their salespeople.

Inspirational motivation

The individually considerate leader is in charge of developing a personal connection with each team member, hearing their concerns, and attending to their unique needs (Bass, 1994; Yammarino *et al.*, 1998). These considerate measures may help to strengthen bonds between team members and establish channels of communication between the leader and each team member. Consider that individualized consideration includes time spent coaching and teaching, careful listening, and acknowledging that each person has unique needs, abilities, and objectives (Bass, 1985, 1990). As a result, efficient team communication may be a suitable precursor to the transformational leadership characteristic.

Personal and Individual attention

Specifically, it involves the degree to which the leader attends to each individual follower's needs

and acts as a mentor or coach and gives respect to and appreciation of the individual's contribution to the team. This fulfills and enhances each individual team members' need for self-fulfillment, and self-worth - and in so doing inspires followers to further achievement and growth. Employee collaboration is an effective method for improving employee performance by sharing between coworkers. In this procedure, each employee will guide the other on how to carry out a task, spreading information, skills, perspectives, and abilities.

Some major weaknesses of Transformational leadership identified by Yukl (1999) include ambiguity underlying its influences and processes, overemphasis of on leadership processes at the dyadic level, the theoretical rationale for differentiating among the behaviors is not clearly explained and transformational leadership theory assumes the heroic leadership stereotype.

Transactional leadership style

Transactional Leadership, also known as managerial leadership, is associated with prevention, focuses on the role of supervision, organization, and group performance; and the leader promotes compliance of his followers through both rewards and punishments. Transactional approaches are not looking to change the future but looking to merely keep things the same. These leaders pay attention to followers' work to find faults and deviations. This type of leadership is effective in crisis and emergency situations, as well as when projects need to be carried out in a specific fashion. Transactional leadership works at the basic levels of need satisfaction, where transactional leaders focus on the lower levels of the hierarchy within the context of Maslow's hierarchy of needs. Rewards are given for good work or positive outcomes by transactional leaders using exchange models but there is also punishment for poor work or negative outcomes, until the problem is corrected. One way that transactional leadership focuses on lower-level needs is by stressing specific task performance (Hargis et al, 2001). Transactional leaders are effective in getting specific tasks completed by managing each portion individually. Consequently, transactional leadership empowers followers to pursue their own self-interest, reduce workplace stress, and focus on specific company goals like improved quality, customer service, cheaper expenses, and higher output (Sadeghi & Pihie, 2012). Two components were identified for

transactional leadership. The components are shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Two components of transactional leadership

Contingent reward

Transactional leaders are concerned with processes rather than forward-thinking ideas. These types of leaders focus on contingent reward (also known as contingent positive reinforcement) or contingent penalization (also known as contingent negative reinforcement). The term "Contingent Reward Transactional (CRT) Leader Behavior" refers to leader behaviors that place a strong emphasis on outlining roles and task requirements and rewarding subordinates in exchange for carrying out contractual responsibilities (Bass, 1998). Contingent rewards (such as praise) are given when the set goals are accomplished on-time, ahead of time, or to keep subordinates working at a good pace at different times throughout completion. Contingent punishments (such as suspensions) are given when performance quality or quantity falls below production standards or goals and tasks are not met at all. In general, contingent reward leaders create rules about job obligations, uphold standards, and decide the repercussions of goal fulfillment. They often provide followers with tangible or intangible support and resources in exchange for their efforts and performance. Often, contingent punishments are handed down on a management-by-exception basis, in which the exception is something going wrong. Within management-by-exception, there are active and passive routes.

Management - by - exception

Active management-by-exception means that the leader continually looks at each subordinate's performance and makes changes to the subordinate's work to make corrections throughout the process. Passive management-by-exception leaders wait for issues to come up before fixing the problems. With transactional leadership being applied to the lower-

level needs and being more managerial in style. Bittel (1964) described management-by-exception as a system of identification and communication that advise the manager when his attention is required: he stays silent when no attention is required. This approach, where a manager manages the execution of subordinate agents, primarily computers or other machines duties - raised the question of what the connection is between a leader and subordinates should be. One of the alternatives for this connection was based on the exception-making rule: don't intervene unless it's absolutely required. The transactional leader is also known as "the manager-by-exception." The leader doesn't get engaged as long as performance expectations are met. Only when performance falls short of a specific level does the leader step in.

Comparison between Transformational Leadership style and Transactional

Leadership style

In summary, James Macgregor Burns distinguished between transactional leaders and transformational by explaining that: transactional leaders are leaders who exchange tangible rewards for the work and loyalty of followers. Transformational leaders are leaders who engage with followers, focus on higher order intrinsic needs, and raise consciousness about the significance of specific outcomes and new ways in which those outcomes might be achieved (Hay, 2012). Transactional leaders tend to be more passive while transformational leaders demonstrate active behaviors that include providing a sense of mission.

Methodology

The systematic literature review conducted systematically databases searched for eligible studies and derived data from the databases PsycINFO, Academic Business Premier, and Google Scholar. Based on this review, the researchers selected 50 articles from amongst 155 papers that were uncovered in the databases and were somehow related to the object of study: "transformational and transactional leadership styles". The results of the search were obtained from websites mentioned above. For the initial search, the search term was transformational and transactional leadership styles: a systematic review of literature. Besides, the study used a series of inclusion criteria to screen papers for the review. These factors included: English language, years of papers

publication >2019, papers that had been published in peer-reviewed journals and dealt with leadership styles (transformational and transactional), as the main aim of the study. As displayed below, a total of only 50 of the original 155 articles were ultimately included in the investigation. The

purpose of this study is to synthesis existing research, highlighting key studies, and to provide suggestions for additional areas of research study. To achieve this end, the authors used the major databases shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Search strategy analytics

Database 2010–2022	Searched Terms	Number of Articles
Academic Business Premier	Transformational leadership and Transactional leadership styles: Systematic Review of Literature from 2010 to 2022	51
Google Scholar	Transformational leadership and Transactional leadership styles: Systematic Review of Literature from 2010 to 2022	19,500
PsycINFO	Transformational leadership and Transactional leadership styles: Systematic Review of Literature from 2010 to 2022	82
Total		19,633.00

Search Strategy, Data Sources, and Screening

The search strategy included the electronic databases shown in Table 1 above. Searches included keywords for articles published between January 2019 and December 2022 that discussed leadership styles, transactional leadership, and transformational leadership.

Inclusion criteria

Included titles, and manuscripts met all inclusion criteria: peer-reviewed studies that discussed leadership styles, transformational leadership, and transactional leadership. This format excluded grey literature.

Screening

The researchers reviewed each titles for inclusion. Studies meeting the inclusion criteria addressed leadership styles and transformational leadership and transactional leadership. Due to the large volume of articles, the authors focused only on reviewed and sort by relevance articles published in English. Figure 4 below illustrates the databases used in this review.

Figure 4: The databases used in this study

Table 2: Stratification of the 23 articles for the Systematic Review

S/N	Authors	Study/Title	Classification
1	Afsar, Bilal Shahjehan, Asad Shah, Syed Imad Wajid, Anees	The mediating role of transformational leadership in the relationship between cultural intelligence and employee voice behavior: A case of hotel employees	Case Study
2	Avolio, B.	Full leadership development: Building the vital forces in organizations.	Book Reviews
3	Avolio, Bruce J. and Bernard M. Bass	Transformational Leadership, Charisma, and Beyond." In Emerging Leadership	Descriptive
4	Bass, B.	Two decades of research and development in transformational leadership	Comparative
5	Bass, B. M. & Avolio, B. J.	Improving organizational effectiveness through transformational leadership	Descriptive
6	Bass, B. M.	Leadership and performance beyond expectations	Book Reviews
7	Bass, B., & Avolio, B.	Full range leadership development: Manual for the Multifactor Leadership Questionnaire	Experimental
8	Bittel, L. R.	Management by exception: Systematizing and simplifying the managerial	Descriptive
9	Burns, J. M	Leadership	Book Reviews
10	Diaz-Saenz, H. R.	Transformational leadership.	
11	Howell, J. M. & Avolio, B. J	Transformational leadership, transactional leadership, locus of control and support for innovation: Key predictors of consolidated-business unit performance	Comparative
12	Joyce E. Bono, Hannah Jackson Foldes, Gregory Vinson, and John P. Muros	"Workplace Emotions: The Role of Supervision and Leadership	Experimental
13	Kelman, Herbert C.	"Compliance, Identification and Internalization: Three Processes of Opinion Change.	Experimental
14	Lowe, K. BKroeck, K.G., & Sivasubramaniam, N	Effectiveness correlates transformational and transactional leadership: A meta-analytic review.	Experimental
15	Perry, A., & Hammond, N.	Systematic reviews: The experiences of a PhD student	Experimental
16	Robert H. Moorman, and Richard Fetter.	Transformational Leader Behaviors and Their Effects on Followers' Trust in Leader, Satisfaction, and Organizational Citizenship Behaviors."	Experimental
17	Ronald F. Piccolo and Jason A. Colquitt	"Transformational Leadership and Job Behaviors: The Mediating Role of Core Job Characteristics	Experimental
18	Sadeghi, A., & Pihie, Z. A. L.	Transformational Leadership and its predictive effects on leadership effectiveness	Experimental
19	Shamir, Boas, Robert J. House, and Michael B. Arthur	The Motivational Effects of Charismatic Leadership: A Self-Concept Based Theory."	Descriptive
20	Sheehan, Maura Garavan, Thomas N. Morley, Michael J.	Transformational leadership and work unit innovation: A dyadic two-wave investigation	Experimental
21	Sheridan, T. B.	Toward a general model of supervisory control	Experimental
22	Sheridan, T. B.	Telerobotics, automation and human supervisory control	Book Reviews
23	Wehrich, H., Cannice, M.V. and Koontz, H.	Management	Book Reviews

Based on our clustering analysis 23 articles were selected for the evidence review. We stratified the research evidence into five broad categories: (1) Case Studies, (2) Comparative studies, (3) Book

Reviews, (4) Descriptive studies, and (5) Experimental studies (Table 2).

The study also compared the Douglas McGregor's Theory Y and Theory X. Where theory X could be synonymous with Transactional Leadership reflecting managers' rule by fear and consequence recognizing that negative behavior is punished and employees are motivated through incentives. Similarly, theory Y and Transformational Leadership are found synonymous, because the theory and the style support the idea that managers work to encourage their workers. Leaders assume the best of their employees. They believe them to be trusting, respectful, and self-motivated. The leaders help to supply the followers with tools they need to excel.

Findings

The findings of the overall systematic literature review showed that transformational leadership encourages higher levels of innovation and creativity measured by divergent thinking among group members, and members in the nominal group condition produced higher levels of creativity and innovation than those in the real group condition (Jung, 2001). In addition, the results showed that the transformational leadership components were still positively connected, it would probably be more beneficial to evaluate the lower and higher-order constructs separately for the purposes of assessment, coaching, and training. The findings demonstrated that transformational leadership is an important predictor of procedural justice, but transactional leadership is an important predictor of distributive justice. In other words, both leadership styles are important predictors of trust in the leaders Ismail *et al.* (2010). This study suggests that the ability of leaders to appropriately implement transformational leadership can lead to increased followers' perceptions of procedural justice. On the other hand, the ability of leaders to properly implement transformational and transactional leadership styles can lead to higher followers' trust in the leaders

Conclusion and Recommendation

The concepts of transformative and transactional leadership styles were first presented by Burns (1978) as a single continuum, with the former at one end and the latter at the other. Both transformational and transactional leadership styles have their various strengths and weaknesses. However, the influence of situational variables on leadership outcomes within the context of both styles of leadership should be ignored. Early empirical investigations provided support for the two distinct leadership

dimensions by demonstrating that these two leadership variables could arise separately from one another. However, as evidenced by the favorable relationships between evaluations for these two leadership styles, the strongest leaders usually exhibited both transformational and transactional leadership (Bass & Avolio, 1993). The six-factor model had the best model fit, according to the findings of the original and replication set of samples, and it held up with very minor shrinkage when tested in the replication sample. There was support for limited construct validity among the transformational and transactional contingent reward leadership scales, even though the six-factor model generated the best match indices. Bass (1985) emphasized the significance of taking into account higher-order elements that underlie the "first-order factors incorporated in his model" in his initial validation work with the multifactor leadership model. In fact, Bass (1985) frequently referred to transformational leadership as a higher-order factor, which prompted the proposed study to explore several higher-order factor models.

Although the three-element method offers a helpful research solution, (Den Hartog *et al.*, 1997) stated that "distinguishing between distinct components of transformational leadership may continue to be beneficial, particularly for training purposes". Future leadership research and practice should not be restricted to a global transformational leadership construct but should instead continue to at least contain each of the elements that make up transformational leadership while also using methods other than surveys to study leadership. Particularly, relatively little has been done to use other approaches, such as observation and interviews, to validate survey ratings of leaders. Using a variety of techniques might help one to distinguish between these various leadership factors more effectively. This is significant not only for research purposes, but it could also serve as a foundation for more accurate training, assessment, and evaluation. The distinction between transactional and transformative leadership may be crucial for training, evaluation, and growth. If a trainee doesn't do a good enough job of clearly outlining what is anticipated of followers in terms of their performance, feedback on how they employed transactional contingent incentive leadership to set expectations with followers may be very significant.

Limitations

There is no research study that does not have limitations. The limitation is that the study did not consider unpublished articles and dissertations. Only the Ebscohost, Academic Search Premier, Business Source Premier, and Google Scholar databases were searched. These databases are comprehensive, but there are possibilities additional articles with specified search criteria could have been found on other databases that were not mentioned.

Implications for Managers' Direction for future research agenda

The systematic review findings reported in this study can suggest some theoretical and practical implications for the imminent study of transformational leadership in organization. For example, this study proved that transformational and transactional leadership can be successfully used to examine how different leadership styles affect individual and organizational performance. There are numerous practical implications that this study may offer to leaders and managers who want to help their employees acquire how to increase their creative and innovative behavior. Amabile (1998), argued that innovation and creativity can be improved through different ways such as altering organizational culture where employees are encouraged to easily discuss and share ideas. In addition, if managers are taught to employ the transformational leadership behaviors discussed in this study, they may help their employees become more intrinsically motivated to put additional efforts into trying out new innovative and creative approaches to their problems. Future experimental studies can investigate how different leadership styles affect innovation and creativity in organization.

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